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APPLYING THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR TO SOCIAL MEDIA HALAL TOURISM PROMOTION

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the role of social media tourism promotion in shaping tourists' psychological determinants and behavioral outcomes toward halal tourism in Surabaya using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) framework. Specifically, this research investigates the influence of social media promotion on attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (PBC), and the effects of these constructs on behavioral and revisit intentions. Data were collected from tourists through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The findings reveal that social media tourism promotion has a significant positive influence on attitude ($p = 0.004$), subjective norms ($p = 0.003$), and perceived behavioral control ($p = 0.001$). These results indicate that social media effectively shapes tourists' evaluations, social perceptions, and perceived ability regarding halal tourism in Surabaya. However, contrary to the classical TPB assumptions, attitude ($p = 0.939$), subjective norms ($p = 0.438$), and perceived behavioral control ($p = 0.237$) do not significantly influence behavioral intention. This suggests that the traditional TPB structure does not fully explain tourists' intention to visit halal tourism destinations in this context. Furthermore, behavioral intention has a significant positive effect on revisit intention ($p = 0.001$), confirming its role as a key predictor of destination loyalty. The study contributes theoretically by highlighting the contextual limitations of TPB in halal tourism settings and emphasizing the importance of external communication factors such as social media promotion. Practically, the findings suggest that halal tourism stakeholders in Surabaya should prioritize strategic, credible, and value-aligned social media campaigns to strengthen tourists' psychological engagement and long-term loyalty.

KEYWORDS: Halal Tourism Promotion; Social Media Marketing; Theory of Planned Behavior; Behavioral Intention; Revisit Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information and communication technology has profoundly transformed the global tourism industry, particularly through the rise of social media as a dominant promotional tool. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok play a central role in shaping how tourists search for information, form perceptions, and make travel decisions (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010; Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014). Within this digital landscape, halal tourism has emerged as a rapidly growing market segment, driven by the increasing demand from Muslim travelers for tourism experiences that comply with Islamic principles, including halal food availability, prayer facilities, and a sharia-compliant environment (Battour & Ismail, 2016).

As one of Indonesia's major metropolitan cities, Surabaya holds significant potential for halal tourism development. Beyond its role as a business and educational hub, Surabaya offers rich historical, cultural, and spiritual attractions that align with Muslim travelers' needs. Prominent halal tourism destinations include Sunan Ampel Mosque, a key Islamic pilgrimage site linked to the Wali Songo heritage; Muhammad Cheng Ho Mosque, which symbolizes cultural acculturation between Islam and Chinese traditions; and Al Akbar Mosque of Surabaya, one of Southeast Asia's largest mosques, known for its grand architecture and comprehensive worship facilities. These destinations attract not only domestic visitors but also international Muslim tourists, particularly from Malaysia, Brunei Darussalam, and the Middle East.

In an increasingly competitive tourism market, local governments and tourism stakeholders in Surabaya must adopt innovative marketing strategies, especially through social media-based halal tourism promotion. Previous studies confirm that social media significantly influences tourists' behavioral intentions by highlighting the unique spiritual and functional values of halal destinations (Javed et al., 2020; Sigala et al., 2012). Visual and narrative digital content showcasing mosque architecture, religious experiences, and Muslim-friendly services can effectively shape tourists' perceptions and motivate actual travel decisions.

Recent empirical evidence supports this argument. Han et al. (2022) found that exposure to religious and educational social media content significantly enhances Muslim tourists' revisit intention, particularly when the content emphasizes Islamic values such as worship convenience, safety, and local hospitality. Similarly, Al-Ansi and Han

(2021) demonstrated that perceived halal service quality is a strong predictor of Muslim tourists' intention to revisit a destination. These findings highlight the importance of visually appealing and value-consistent promotional content in strengthening tourists' behavioral outcomes.

To explain how social media promotion influences tourist behavior, this study adopts the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991). TPB posits that behavioral intention is determined by three key factors: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (PBC). In halal tourism, attitude reflects positive evaluations of Islamic travel experiences; subjective norms relate to social influences from family, religious communities, and opinion leaders; and PBC refers to tourists' perceptions of their ability to travel based on information access, facilities, and logistical convenience.

Social media plays a crucial role in strengthening all components of the TPB. User-generated content, testimonials, and visual depictions of halal facilities can foster positive attitudes toward destinations (Munar & Jacobsen, 2014). Endorsements from Muslim influencers, religious figures, and online communities reinforce subjective norms by creating social encouragement to visit halal destinations (Chatzigeorgiou, 2017). Furthermore, social media enhances perceived behavioral control by providing accessible information on transportation routes, halal accommodations, restaurants, and prayer schedules, thereby increasing tourists' confidence in undertaking halal travel (Han et al., 2022).

Despite growing global interest in halal tourism, empirical studies integrating social media tourism promotion, TPB constructs, and revisit intention in a local Indonesian context remain limited. Most prior research focuses on destinations such as Malaysia, Turkey, or the UAE, while cities like Surabaya have received relatively little scholarly attention. This gap is notable given Surabaya's large Muslim population and strong potential to become a leading halal tourism destination in eastern Indonesia.

Therefore, this study aims to address this gap by examining how social media-based halal tourism promotion influences attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and revisit intention in the context of halal tourism in Surabaya. The findings are expected to contribute theoretically to extending TPB in halal tourism research and to provide practical insights for destination managers and policymakers in designing effective digital marketing strategies aligned with Islamic values.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theory Of Planned Behavior

The conceptual model of this study is grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which explains how individual behavioral intentions are shaped by psychological determinants, namely attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. According to Icek Ajzen (1991), attitude refers to an individual's positive or negative evaluation of performing a particular behavior, while subjective norm reflects perceived social pressure from significant others to engage or not engage in that behavior. Perceived behavioral control represents an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behavior, which is influenced by past experiences and perceived resources.

In the context of halal tourism promotion through social media, these TPB constructs are operationalized to explain how exposure to tourism-related content may shape users' psychological responses and behavioral intentions. Social media platforms serve as interactive marketing channels that can influence consumers' perceptions, attitudes, and social norms through information sharing, visual storytelling, and peer interaction (Hajli, 2015; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010). Consequently, social media tourism promotion is expected to strengthen positive attitudes toward halal tourism, reinforce subjective norms through online community influence, and enhance perceived behavioral control by providing accessible information about halal-friendly destinations. These relationships collectively contribute to shaping individuals' intentions to visit or revisit halal tourism destinations. By integrating digital marketing perspectives with TPB, the proposed conceptual framework provides a comprehensive explanation of how psychological factors and online promotional strategies jointly influence tourists' behavioral responses in the halal tourism context.

2.2. Social Media Promotion

Social media has become a dominant channel in tourism promotion strategies while simultaneously shaping tourists' travel experiences. A study by Javed et al. (2020) demonstrates that social media marketing (SMM) significantly strengthens brand loyalty, thereby increasing purchase intention in the post-COVID-19 travel context. These findings indicate that social media promotion plays a crucial role in influencing tourists' behavioral responses by providing accessible information, engaging visual content, and interactive communication channels. Through platforms such as Instagram, TikTok,

YouTube, and Facebook, tourism organizations can present destinations more dynamically and reach wider audiences, allowing potential tourists to explore destinations virtually before making travel decisions.

Furthermore, social media platforms enable tourism stakeholders to disseminate promotional content in various forms, including videos, travel blogs, user-generated content, and influencer endorsements. Such content helps tourists develop perceptions about destinations, evaluate available tourism facilities, and form expectations about travel experiences. Previous studies also emphasize that social media promotion enhances tourists' awareness and interest in destinations by providing real-time information, visual storytelling, and interactive engagement between destinations and potential visitors (Azhar, 2023). As a result, social media has evolved beyond a simple communication tool and now functions as a strategic marketing instrument that significantly shapes tourists' perceptions, destination attractiveness, and travel intentions.

2.3. Behavior Intention

Behavioral intention, defined as tourists' intention to visit a destination, serves as a key proxy for actual travel behavior. Crofton and Parker (2024, cited in Javed et al.) report that social media usage directly increases behavioral intention, particularly among millennials who frequently consume travel-related content on platforms such as YouTube and Instagram (Javed et al., 2020).

Additionally, Tang et al. (2023), using an extended TPB model, found that social media usage significantly influences tourists' intention to visit "internet celebrity cities." However, usage frequency does not act as a significant moderating variable. Moreover, Azhar et al. (2022) emphasize the critical role of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) on social media in shaping attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, ultimately influencing revisit intention in the post-pandemic tourism environment.

2.4. Revisit Intention

Recent studies indicate that social media also plays a vital role in enhancing revisit intention. A post-pandemic study published in the *Future Business Journal* (2022) employed an extended TPB framework incorporating eWOM and destination image, revealing that eWOM significantly shapes attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and tourists' intention to revisit a destination.

Furthermore, Demirel and Çiftci (2021), as reiterated by Huang and Hsu, found that perceived behavioral control and subjective norms positively influence visit intention, with long-term implications for destination loyalty and repeat visitation. Earlier research by Abbassi (2019) extended the TPB framework by demonstrating that perceived value and tourist satisfaction mediate the relationship between perceived service quality and revisit intention. This finding is particularly relevant for halal tourism destinations, where consistent delivery of sharia-compliant service quality is essential to fostering repeat visits.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research approach to examine the influence of social media-based halal tourism promotion on tourists' behavioral intention and revisit intention, grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). A cross-sectional survey design was applied, and data were collected using a structured questionnaire distributed to Muslim tourists who had visited halal

tourism destinations in Surabaya, actively used social media platforms, and had been exposed to halal tourism promotional content. A purposive sampling technique was used, resulting in 100 valid responses. This sample size is considered adequate for Covariance-Based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), as it exceeds the minimum recommended threshold for SEM-AMOS analysis.

All constructs were measured using previously validated indicators and assessed on a five-point Likert scale. Data analysis was conducted using Structural Equation Modeling with AMOS, following a two-step approach. First, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed to evaluate the measurement model, focusing on construct reliability and validity through standardized factor loadings, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Second, the structural model was tested to examine the hypothesized relationships among variables. Model fit was assessed using multiple goodness-of-fit indices, including CMIN/df, CFI, TLI, and RMSEA. At the same time, the significance of path relationships was evaluated based on critical ratios and p-values.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of this study, which is grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior developed by Icek Ajzen. The model proposes that social media tourism promotion acts as a key external factor that shapes tourists' psychological responses toward halal tourism destinations. In the context of halal tourism in Surabaya, social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube play an important role in disseminating information about Muslim-friendly attractions, halal culinary experiences, and Islamic heritage sites. Through visually appealing promotional content, travel videos, and user-generated reviews, potential tourists are exposed to

information regarding halal facilities, prayer spaces, and Islamic cultural experiences available in Surabaya. This exposure is expected to influence three core psychological determinants of tourist behavior within the Theory of Planned Behavior: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

In this framework, attitude reflects tourists' overall evaluation of halal tourism experiences in Surabaya. Positive exposure to destinations such as the Sunan Ampel Mosque, the Cheng Ho Mosque Surabaya, and the Al-Akbar National Mosque Surabaya may strengthen tourists' favorable perceptions toward Surabaya as a halal-friendly

destination. Meanwhile, subjective norms refer to the perceived social influence from family members, friends, or online communities that encourage individuals to visit halal tourism destinations. In the digital tourism environment, recommendations, travel experiences, and endorsements shared through social media can shape collective perceptions and create social encouragement to explore halal tourism sites in Surabaya. Furthermore, perceived behavioral control reflects tourists' perception of their ability and resources to undertake halal travel. Information shared through social media regarding transportation access, availability of halal-certified restaurants, prayer facilities, and Muslim-friendly accommodations may enhance tourists' confidence in their ability to travel comfortably and conveniently within Surabaya.

The framework further proposes that these three psychological determinants collectively influence tourists' behavioral intention to visit halal tourism destinations in Surabaya. Behavioral intention represents the motivational readiness of individuals to perform a specific behavior, in this case visiting halal tourism sites. When tourists develop strong intentions to visit Surabaya's halal attractions, this intention may eventually translate into actual travel behavior. Finally, behavioral intention is hypothesized to positively influence revisit intention, which reflects tourists' willingness to return to the destination after their initial visit. In the context of halal tourism development in Surabaya, revisit intention is particularly important because repeat visitors contribute to sustainable tourism growth, strengthen destination loyalty, and generate positive word-of-mouth promotion among Muslim travelers. Therefore, the conceptual framework highlights the strategic role of social media tourism promotion in shaping tourists' psychological perceptions and behavioral intentions, which ultimately encourage

repeat visitation to halal tourism destinations in Surabaya.

3.1. Measurement

To ensure the validity and reliability of the research model, each construct in this study was operationalized using measurement items adapted from established studies in tourism and consumer behavior literature. The constructs examined include social media promotion of halal tourism, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, behavioral intention, and revisit intention. These variables are primarily grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Icek Ajzen (1991), which suggests that individuals' behavioral intentions are influenced by their attitudes toward the behavior, perceived social pressure, and perceived control over performing the behavior. The measurement items were adapted from previous empirical studies to ensure conceptual consistency and empirical robustness within the context of tourism marketing and social media research. Respondents were asked to evaluate each item using a Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The indicators for social media promotion were adapted from studies on social media marketing and online tourism information (Alalwan, 2018; Xiang & Gretzel, 2010), while the TPB constructs attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and behavioral intention were derived from previous TPB-based tourism studies (Han et al., 2010; Lam & Hsu, 2006). Furthermore, the revisit intention items were adapted from research on tourism loyalty and behavioral intention (Baker & Crompton, 2000; Chen & Tsai, 2007). The detailed operationalization of each variable, including indicators, measurement items, and sources, is presented in Table I.

Table I: Measurement.

Variable	Measurement	Source
Social Media Promotion of Halal Tourism	Social media provides useful information about halal tourism destinations.	(Xiang & Gretzel, 2010; Alalwan, 2018)
	Halal tourism promotional content on social media is entertaining.	(Alalwan, 2018)
	Social media allows users to interact with halal tourism promotional content.	(Hajli, 2015)
	Information about halal tourism shared on social media is trustworthy.	(Fileri & McLeay, 2014)
Attitude	Visiting halal tourism destinations promoted on social media is a good idea.	(Ajzen, 1991; Jalilvand & Samiei, 2012)
	I have a favorable attitude toward halal tourism destinations promoted on social media.	(Ajzen, 1991)
	Halal tourism destinations promoted on social media are attractive to visit.	(Jalilvand & Samiei, 2012)
Subjective Norm	My family encourages me to visit halal tourism destinations.	(Ajzen, 1991)
	My friends think that visiting halal tourism destinations is a good idea.	(Han et al., 2010)
	People who are important to me support my decision to visit halal tourism destinations.	(Ajzen, 1991)
Perceived	I feel capable of visiting halal tourism destinations.	(Ajzen, 1991)

Behavioral Control	I have sufficient resources (time, money) to visit halal tourism destinations.	(Han et al., 2010)
	It is easy for me to visit halal tourism destinations if I want to.	(Ajzen, 1991)
Behavioral Intention	I intend to visit halal tourism destinations promoted on social media.	(Ajzen, 1991; Lam & Hsu, 2006)
	I plan to visit halal tourism destinations in the future.	(Lam & Hsu, 2006)
	I am willing to choose halal tourism destinations for my travel.	(Han et al., 2010)
Revisit Intention	I intend to revisit halal tourism destinations in the future.	(Baker & Crompton, 2000)
	I would prefer to revisit halal tourism destinations rather than other destinations.	(Chen & Tsai, 2007)
	I am likely to revisit halal tourism destinations if given the opportunity.	(Chen & Tsai, 2007)

4. RESULT

Figure 2: Sem Framework.

4.1. Loading Faktor

The loading factor reflects the strength of the relationship between an observed indicator and its underlying latent construct. In Structural Equation

Modeling using AMOS, an indicator is considered valid when its standardized loading exceeds a minimum threshold of 0.50. However, values above 0.70 are generally preferred to ensure stronger convergent validity (Hair et al., 2017).

Table II: Loading Factor.

Indicator	Latent Variable	Estimate
SMTP2	PMS	0,670
SMTP3	PMS	0,595
SMTP4	PMS	0,716
SN1	SN	0,660
SN2	SN	0,562
PBC1	PBC	0,591
PBC2	PBC	0,722
AT1	ATT	0,504
AT2	ATT	0,690
BI1	BI	0,612
BI2	BI	0,536
RI1	RI	0,617
RI2	RI	0,615

4.2. Model Fit

The model fit evaluation indicates that the structural model provides an acceptable overall fit, as indicated by multiple goodness-of-fit indices. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)

value of 0.024 is below the recommended threshold of 0.08, indicating an acceptable approximation of the model to the population covariance matrix (Hair et al., 2022; Kline, 2023). The CMIN/DF (χ^2/df) value of 1.125 is also within the acceptable range below 5.00,

suggesting a reasonable level of model parsimony and fit. Regarding incremental fit indices, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI = 0.967), Comparative Fit Index (CFI = 0.979), and Incremental Fit Index (IFI = 0.981) all exceed the recommended minimum threshold of 0.90, indicating good comparative fit relative to the null model (Hair *et al.*, 2022). Although CFI does not exceed the more conservative threshold of 0.95, values above 0.90 are generally considered acceptable in complex models with large samples.

However, the Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI = 0.931) and Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI = 0.872) fall slightly below the recommended cutoff of 0.90.

Despite this, recent SEM literature suggests that GFI and AGFI are sensitive to sample size and model complexity and should not be used as sole indicators of model adequacy (Kline, 2023). Contemporary methodological guidance emphasizes RMSEA and incremental fit indices such as CFI and TLI as more robust indicators of model fit. Overall, given that the majority of key fit indices (RMSEA, CMIN/DF, TLI, CFI, and IFI) meet acceptable criteria, the structural model can be considered adequately and acceptably fit to the data, allowing further interpretation of the structural relationships.

Table III: Hypothesis Testing.

	Cut-Off	Value	Criteria
p-value		0,225	Fit
RMSEA	< 0,08	0,024	Fit
CMIN/DF	< 5,00	1,125	Fit
GFI	> 0,9	0,931	Fit
AGFI	>0,9	0,872	Not Fit
TLI	>0,95	0,967	Fit
CFI	>0,95	0,979	Fit
IFI	>0,9	0,981	Fit

4.3. Hypothesis Testing

Significance of path coefficients is tested using

bootstrapping, which provides p-values ≤ 0.05 indicate statistical significance at the 5% level (two-tailed).

Table VI: Hypothesis Testing.

Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Criteria
Social Media Tourist Promotion » Subjective Norms	,641	,220	2,907	,004	Significant
Social Media Tourist Promotion: Perceived Behavior Control	,499	,170	2,928	,003	Significant
Social Media Tourist Promotion » Attitude Subjective Norms » Behavior Intention	1,360	,334	4,067	,001	Significant
Perceived Behavior Control » Behavior Intention	,677	,872	1,776	,438	Not Significant
Attitude » Behavior Intention	1,432	1,211	1,182	,237	Not Significant
Behavior Intention » Revisit Intention	,013	,170	,077	,939	Not Significant
	,951	,254	3,738	,001	Significant

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Social Media Tourism Promotion Significantly Influences Tourists' Attitudes Toward Halal Tourism in Surabaya

The results of this study indicate that social media tourism promotion has a significant effect on tourists' attitudes toward halal tourism in Surabaya. The structural model analysis shows an estimated value of 1.360, and the p-value is 0.001, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05. These findings confirm that social media promotion plays a significant role in shaping tourists' attitudes toward halal tourism destinations. This result supports the assumption that exposure to tourism-related promotional content

on social media platforms can positively influence individuals' perceptions and evaluations of a destination.

Within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior developed by Ajzen (1991), attitude refers to an individual's positive or negative evaluation of performing a particular behavior. In the context of halal tourism, this evaluation is formed through beliefs about the benefits, values, and experiences associated with visiting halal-friendly destinations. Social media serves as an important communication channel, providing information, visual representations, and user-generated content that shape tourists' cognitive and affective evaluations of a destination. When halal tourism destinations are

promoted through visually appealing and informative content highlighting halal food, prayer facilities, Islamic cultural heritage, and spiritual tourism experiences, tourists are more likely to develop favorable attitudes toward visiting those destinations.

This finding is consistent with previous studies that highlight the important role of social media in shaping tourists' perceptions and attitudes toward tourism destinations. For instance, Xiang and Gretzel (2010) emphasize that social media has transformed the way tourists search for and evaluate travel information, making it one of the most influential sources in shaping destination perceptions. Similarly, Alalwan (2018) argues that social media marketing activities significantly influence consumer attitudes because they combine informative, entertaining, and interactive content, thereby enhancing user engagement. In the tourism context, Shang et al. (2021) found that exposure to tourism-related social media content contributes significantly to the development of positive tourist attitudes, as social media enables more authentic, personalized, and emotionally engaging communication. Furthermore, Javed et al. (2020) demonstrate that social media tourism promotion can strengthen destination trust and foster favorable attitudes, particularly when the promotional content is perceived as credible and relevant to tourists' values and travel motivations.

In Surabaya, social media promotion can effectively highlight halal tourism attractions such as the Sunan Ampel Mosque, Cheng Ho Mosque Surabaya, and the Al-Akbar National Mosque Surabaya, which are important Islamic religious and cultural landmarks in the city. Through visual storytelling, travel experiences, and testimonials shared on platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, these destinations can be portrayed as not only attractive tourist sites but also spiritually meaningful destinations for Muslim tourists. Consequently, exposure to such promotional content strengthens tourists' perceptions that Surabaya offers destinations that are compatible with their religious values and travel preferences. Overall, the findings suggest that social media tourism promotion plays a crucial role in shaping favorable attitudes toward halal tourism destinations. By delivering authentic, informative, and value-oriented promotional messages, social media platforms can effectively influence tourists' cognitive and emotional evaluations, thereby strengthening positive attitudes toward visiting halal tourism destinations in Surabaya.

5.2. Social Media Tourism Promotion Significantly Influences Tourists' Subjective Norms Toward Halal Tourism in Surabaya

The results of this study indicate that social media tourism promotion has a significant effect on tourists' attitudes toward halal tourism in Surabaya. The structural model analysis shows an estimated value of 0,499 and the p-value is $0.004 < 0.05$. This finding suggests that exposure to halal tourism promotional content on social media platforms contributes to shaping tourists' perceptions regarding social expectations and social approval related to visiting halal tourism destinations.

Within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Ajzen (1991), subjective norms refer to an individual's perception of social pressure from important referent groups, such as family members, friends, or communities, regarding whether a particular behavior should be performed. In the contemporary digital environment, however, the formation of subjective norms extends beyond traditional interpersonal interactions to include virtual social influences mediated through social media platforms. Social media enables individuals to observe the opinions, experiences, and recommendations shared by broader online communities, including Muslim influencers, religious figures, travel bloggers, and members of Islamic lifestyle communities.

Previous studies have demonstrated that social media plays a crucial role in shaping social influence and normative beliefs within tourism contexts. For example, Xiang and Gretzel (2010) argue that social media platforms have become dominant sources of travel-related information and social influence, enabling tourists to observe and evaluate others' travel behaviors. Similarly, Shang et al. (2021) explain that digital interactions such as likes, comments, and shares reinforce perceived social approval, which strengthens normative pressure within online communities. In addition, Wu, Mohamed, and Fan (2023) demonstrate that exposure to tourism content endorsed or recommended by peers significantly influences subjective norms, as individuals tend to perceive frequently shared or recommended behaviors as socially acceptable and desirable.

In the context of halal tourism, these mechanisms are particularly relevant because travel decisions are often influenced by religious values and community expectations. Social media promotion that highlights halal-friendly tourism experiences, such as visits to the Sunan Ampel Mosque, Cheng Ho Mosque Surabaya, and the Al-Akbar National Mosque Surabaya, can shape collective perceptions within

Muslim communities, leading them to view such destinations as appropriate and socially supported travel choices. Visual narratives, testimonials from Muslim travelers, and endorsements from religious influencers or hijrah communities may further reinforce the perception that traveling to halal destinations aligns with the values and expectations of the broader Muslim community.

Furthermore, Al-Ansi and Han (2021) emphasize that endorsements from trusted figures within Muslim communities can significantly influence the formation of social norms related to halal tourism preferences. When individuals observe respected figures or community members promoting halal travel experiences, they are more likely to perceive such behavior as socially desirable and consistent with shared religious values. Consequently, the presence of supportive narratives and endorsements on social media contributes to the formation of stronger subjective norms that encourage participation in halal tourism. Overall, these findings suggest that social media tourism promotion plays an important role in shaping subjective norms by generating perceived social support and normative pressure from digital communities. As Muslim travelers increasingly rely on online networks to evaluate travel choices, social media platforms become influential spaces where collective expectations and shared values regarding halal tourism are constructed and reinforced.

5.3. Social Media Tourism Promotion Significantly Influences Tourists' Perceived Behavioral Control Toward Halal Tourism in Surabaya

The results of this study indicate that social media tourism promotion has a significant influence on tourists' perceived behavioral control toward halal tourism in Surabaya, with a p -value of $0.003 < 0.05$. This finding suggests that exposure to halal tourism promotional content on social media platforms enhances tourists' confidence in their ability to organize and undertake halal travel activities. Perceived behavioral control (PBC) refers to the extent to which individuals believe that they possess the ability, resources, and opportunities to perform a particular behavior, such as visiting halal tourism destinations.

Within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Icek Ajzen (1991), perceived behavioral control reflects an individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to perform a behavior based on available resources, knowledge, and opportunities. In the context of tourism, this

perception is strongly influenced by the availability and accessibility of travel-related information. Social media platforms provide a wide range of travel information, including destination accessibility, transportation options, accommodation availability, and other facilities, helping tourists evaluate whether a trip is feasible and manageable.

Previous studies have highlighted the significant role of social media in strengthening tourists' perceptions of control over travel decisions. For instance, Xiang and Gretzel (2010) emphasize that social media has become one of the most important sources of tourism information, enabling travelers to obtain practical and experiential knowledge from other users. Similarly, Shang *et al.* (2021) demonstrate that social media contributes to the development of perceived behavioral control by providing reliable information and user-generated experiences that serve as practical references for prospective tourists. Travel-related content such as itinerary recommendations, halal restaurant reviews, Muslim-friendly travel guides, and destination accessibility information shared on platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube can significantly enhance tourists' confidence in their ability to visit a destination.

In the context of halal tourism in Surabaya, social media promotion can highlight various Muslim-friendly facilities that support tourists' travel convenience. Information on prayer facilities at the Al-Akbar National Mosque in Surabaya, halal culinary options in the Sunan Ampel Mosque area, and transportation access to the Cheng Ho Mosque in Surabaya can strengthen tourists' perceptions that traveling to Surabaya is convenient and compatible with Islamic values. In addition, the interactive features of social media allow users to ask questions, share travel experiences, and obtain recommendations from other travelers, thereby further reducing uncertainty and strengthening perceived behavioral control.

Supporting this argument, Wu, Mohamed, and Fan (2023) find that social media enhances perceived behavioral control by improving information accessibility and fostering tourists' self-efficacy, particularly when travelers rely on others' experiences. Similarly, Javed *et al.* (2020) emphasize that user-generated content, especially from fellow travelers or Muslim influencers, plays an important role in strengthening perceived behavioral control because it is often perceived as more authentic and relatable than formal promotional materials produced by official institutions.

Overall, the findings suggest that social media

tourism promotion significantly enhances tourists' perceived behavioral control by providing accessible, credible, and experience-based information about halal tourism destinations. By reducing uncertainty and improving tourists' confidence in planning and undertaking halal travel, social media promotion is an important mechanism for facilitating travel decision-making among Muslim tourists.

5.4. The Non-Significant Effects of Attitude, Subjective Norms, And Perceived Behavioral Control on Tourists' Behavioral Intention Toward Halal Tourism in Surabaya

Behavioral intention represents the primary dependent variable in this study, reflecting the extent to which individuals intend to perform a particular behavior, specifically visiting halal tourism destinations in Surabaya. Within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Icek Ajzen (1991), behavioral intention is theoretically determined by three core constructs: attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control (PBC). These constructs represent individuals' evaluation of the behavior, perceived social pressure, and perceived ability to perform the behavior. In many tourism studies, these three factors have been found to significantly predict travel intention. However, the findings of the present study reveal that none of these constructs significantly influence behavioral intention in the context of halal tourism in Surabaya. This result suggests that additional psychological, experiential, or situational factors beyond the traditional TPB structure may influence the formation of tourists' intentions in this context.

The empirical results indicate that attitude does not have a significant effect on behavioral intention, with a p-value of 0.939 (>0.05). This finding suggests that tourists' positive or negative evaluations of halal tourism destinations in Surabaya are not sufficient to shape their intention to visit directly. Although respondents may perceive destinations such as the Al-Akbar National Mosque Surabaya, Cheng Ho Mosque Surabaya, and the Sunan Ampel Mosque positively, these favorable perceptions do not automatically translate into a concrete intention to travel. One possible explanation is that tourists may already consider halal attributes as a basic or expected feature in a predominantly Muslim destination such as Surabaya. As a result, positive attitudes toward halal facilities may not serve as a strong differentiating factor in travel intention. In addition, tourists may evaluate halal destinations positively at a cognitive level, but other practical considerations, such as time availability, travel

budget, competing destinations, or personal travel priorities, may ultimately determine whether they intend to visit. This indicates that while attitude reflects a favorable perception, it may not be sufficiently strong to drive behavioral commitment in the form of travel intention.

Similarly, subjective norm does not significantly influence behavioral intention, as indicated by a p-value of 0.438 (>0.05). This finding implies that social influence from family members, friends, or religious communities does not significantly determine tourists' intention to visit halal tourism destinations in Surabaya. In many contexts, particularly in collectivist cultures, social approval and encouragement often play an important role in shaping individual behavior. However, the results of this study suggest that tourism decisions are perceived more as personal choices than as behaviors strongly influenced by social expectations. Travel activities are often associated with personal preferences, leisure motivations, and individual lifestyle choices, which may reduce the influence of social pressure. Furthermore, in the digital era, travelers are increasingly exposed to diverse information sources from social media, travel platforms, and online communities. These independent information sources may reduce the reliance on traditional reference groups when making travel decisions. Consequently, the role of subjective norms in shaping behavioral intention may become less dominant than that of other motivational or experiential factors.

Furthermore, perceived behavioral control (PBC) does not significantly influence behavioral intention, with a p-value of 0.237 (>0.05). This result indicates that respondents' perceptions regarding their ability, resources, or opportunities to visit halal tourism destinations in Surabaya do not significantly determine their intention to travel. In the context of tourism, perceived behavioral control typically reflects factors such as financial resources, travel accessibility, availability of transportation, time constraints, and perceived convenience of travel arrangements. However, the non-significant relationship found in this study may indicate that respondents already perceive traveling to Surabaya as relatively easy and feasible. Because Surabaya is a major urban destination with well-developed infrastructure, transportation access, and abundant halal facilities, respondents may not perceive significant barriers when considering travel. When perceived difficulty is low and travel feasibility is taken for granted, perceived behavioral control may lose its predictive strength in explaining behavioral

intention.

Overall, these findings suggest that the classical structure of the Theory of Planned Behavior may not fully explain behavioral intention in the context of halal tourism in Surabaya. The absence of significant relationships between attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control with behavioral intention indicates that other factors may play a more dominant role in shaping tourists' intentions. In tourism research, variables such as destination image, emotional experience, travel motivation, religiosity, digital engagement, and marketing communication are often identified as important determinants of travel intention. In particular, experiential and emotional aspects of tourism may have a stronger influence on intention compared to purely cognitive evaluations. Therefore, future research is encouraged to extend the TPB framework by integrating additional constructs that capture experiential, emotional, and contextual dimensions of tourism behavior, particularly in the rapidly evolving landscape of halal tourism and digital travel promotion.

5.5. Intention Significantly Influences Tourists' Revisit Intention Toward Halal Tourism in Surabaya

The findings of this study indicate that behavioral intention has a significant effect on tourists' revisit intention toward halal tourism in Surabaya, as evidenced by a p-value of 0.001, well below the commonly accepted significance threshold of 0.05. This result confirms that tourists with a strong intention to visit halal tourism destinations are more likely to form an intention to revisit them in the future. In other words, behavioral intention is an important psychological predictor of tourists' future travel decisions and loyalty toward a destination.

Within the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Icek Ajzen, behavioral intention represents an individual's motivational readiness and commitment to perform a particular behavior. According to this theory, behavioral intention is the most immediate antecedent of actual behavior, meaning that individuals with strong intentions are more likely to translate those intentions into action. In the context of tourism, behavioral intention reflects tourists' willingness and commitment to engage in travel activities, including visiting specific destinations and participating in the experiences they offer.

In the context of halal tourism, behavioral intention reflects tourists' willingness to engage in travel experiences that are compatible with Islamic

principles, such as the availability of halal food, accessible prayer facilities, and a Muslim-friendly environment. When tourists develop a strong intention to visit halal tourism destinations, they are more likely to form a deeper psychological attachment to those destinations. As a result, once tourists have visited and experienced the destination, this initial intention can evolve into a desire to revisit the destination in the future. The significant relationship identified in this study suggests that tourists who initially plan to visit halal tourism destinations in Surabaya, such as the Sunan Ampel Mosque, Cheng Ho Mosque Surabaya, and the Al-Akbar National Mosque Surabaya, are more likely to form intentions to return after their initial visit.

This finding is consistent with previous tourism studies, which emphasize that behavioral intention is a crucial predictor of destination loyalty and revisit behavior. Research by Chen and Tsai demonstrates that tourists who exhibit strong behavioral intentions toward a destination tend to show higher levels of satisfaction and loyalty, which subsequently lead to repeat visitation. Similarly, studies in tourism behavior suggest that when tourists develop a strong pre-visit intention, they are more likely to maintain a favorable evaluation of the destination after experiencing it, thereby increasing their likelihood of revisiting.

Furthermore, behavioral intention often reflects a cumulative psychological evaluation formed through various cognitive and affective processes. Although the constructs of attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control did not significantly influence behavioral intention in the previous analysis, the formation of behavioral intention itself still represents an internal motivational state that encourages individuals to engage in tourism activities. In many cases, tourists who have already formed a strong intention to visit a destination tend to seek additional information, imagine their future experiences, and mentally commit to the trip. This psychological commitment strengthens their attachment to the destination and increases the probability of future visits.

In the context of halal tourism, revisit intention plays a particularly important role because Muslim tourists often prioritize destinations that consistently provide services aligned with Islamic values. Destinations that offer halal-certified food, accessible mosques, Islamic cultural attractions, and a supportive religious atmosphere tend to generate a sense of spiritual comfort and emotional satisfaction among Muslim travelers. When tourists' initial behavioral intention is fulfilled through positive

travel experiences such as convenient access to worship facilities, authentic Islamic heritage sites, and a welcoming Muslim-friendly environment, the likelihood of revisit intention increases substantially.

Overall, the results of this study highlight the importance of strengthening tourists' behavioral intention as a strategic approach to fostering revisit intention in halal tourism destinations. By developing promotional strategies, digital tourism campaigns, and destination experiences that reinforce tourists' intentions to visit, tourism stakeholders in Surabaya can enhance destination loyalty and encourage repeat visitation among Muslim travelers.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to analyze the influence of social media tourism promotion on tourists' behavioral formation toward halal tourism in Surabaya through the lens of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). The findings demonstrate that social media promotion plays a crucial role in shaping tourists' psychological determinants, namely attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The significant relationships indicate that exposure to credible, informative, and value-oriented halal tourism content on social media platforms strengthens tourists' positive evaluations, perceived social encouragement, and confidence in their ability to travel in accordance with Islamic principles.

However, the results reveal that the three core TPB constructs, attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, do not significantly influence behavioral intention. This finding suggests that, within the context of halal tourism in Surabaya, the traditional TPB framework does not fully explain the formation of travel intention. One possible explanation is that halal tourism represents a niche tourism segment in which travel decisions are influenced not only by cognitive evaluations but also by value-based and experiential considerations. Other contextual factors beyond the classical TPB components, such as destination image, religiosity, emotional attachment to the destination, or prior travel experiences, may therefore shape tourists' intentions. These elements may play a more

dominant role in forming tourists' intentions, particularly when halal tourism is perceived not merely as a travel activity but as a lifestyle aligned with religious values and identity.

Despite this, behavioral intention significantly influences revisit intention, confirming its central role in predicting destination loyalty. Tourists who exhibit strong initial intentions are more likely to develop commitments to revisit halal tourism destinations in Surabaya, particularly when their experiences align with expectations and when the destination successfully delivers halal-compliant services and meaningful travel experiences.

Overall, this study offers several theoretical contributions. First, it contributes to the halal tourism literature by providing empirical evidence that the explanatory power of the classical TPB model may be limited when applied to specialized tourism contexts such as halal tourism. This finding suggests the need to extend TPB by incorporating additional constructs that reflect the unique characteristics of Muslim travel behavior. Variables such as religiosity, destination image, tourist engagement, and emotional attachment may complement TPB in explaining behavioral intention more comprehensively. Second, this study highlights the role of social media promotion as an antecedent shaping TPB variable, demonstrating that digital promotional content can influence tourists' psychological readiness even when the direct effects of TPB constructs on intention are not significant. By integrating social media promotion with TPB, this research enriches the theoretical understanding of how digital marketing communication contributes to the formation of halal tourism behavior.

From a practical perspective, the findings emphasize that social media promotion is a powerful strategic tool for shaping tourists' perceptions and long-term loyalty. Therefore, halal tourism stakeholders in Surabaya should continue to invest in authentic, transparent, and value-consistent digital promotion strategies that highlight halal facilities, cultural experiences, and Muslim-friendly services. Strengthening storytelling, visual experiences, and user-generated content may further enhance engagement and encourage repeat visitation to halal tourism destinations.

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